

An Overview of Literature on Assessment for Learning informing Irish Primary Physical Education

Abstract:

Literature examining the adoption of Assessment for Learning (AfL) in Physical Education (PE) reveals shortcomings in both understanding of assessment practices and their practical implementation among teachers. This is despite AfL's importance in enhancing student learning and guiding instructional practice. Recent studies suggest several issues at play: low assessment literacy, deficits in support networks and a lingering view that PE is a low-stakes curricular area. Literature identifying successful strategies and supports is limited. However, available research indicates some success with interventions aimed at improving assessment practices, integration of technology, and developing networks among PE teachers. This paper examines extant literature for the benefits of integrating AfL into PE, identifies existing barriers to its implementation, and proposes support strategies to address these challenges, offering valuable insights for the future development of Irish primary PE.

Key words: Assessment, Physical Education (PE), Assessment for Learning (AfL), Formative Assessment, Irish Primary Education.

Key Points:

- Despite decades of advocacy for inclusion of Assessment for Learning (AfL) across the curriculum, uptake in Physical Education has remained stubbornly low.
- Limited research from both international and Irish contexts points to some benefits for student engagement and learning when AfL is included in PE, however, the same studies also highlight many barriers to AfL's implementation in PE.
- Support for AfL enactment is needed to address the dominance of sporadic and inconsistent summative assessment as the prevailing form of assessment in PE.

Introduction

Assessment for Learning (AfL) has been promoted as an essential element of quality teaching and learning for the past 30 years (Wiliam, 2007). Its inclusion in physical education (PE) has been inconsistent at best. Due to lack of research in the area, AfL enactment levels are difficult to accurately ascertain. Assessment in PE is viewed as low stakes and is often easily avoided. (DinanThompson & Penney, 2015; MacPhail and Murphy, 2017). When assessment in PE is taking place, it continues to be dominated by more traditional, summative forms of assessment often valuing fitness and end of unit performance (Lorente-Catalan and Kirk, 2016, Lyngstad et. al, 2022). Nevertheless, some more recent studies have reported progress in the areas of AfL enactment and assessment literacy of PE teachers, however this has been gradual and largely confined to PE specialist teachers in secondary school contexts. (González-Rivera et al., 2023; Moura et al., 2023). One recent review of formative and shared assessment in PE from Spain and Chile shows promising levels of implementation but acknowledges this PE assessment model is relatively “unknown in the international literature” (Herrero-González et al., 2024, p.506).

Identifying and addressing the barriers that exist for teachers in enacting AfL in PE is essential to see increases in use and improved student outcomes (Herrero-González et al., 2024). This will also aid in the advancement of PE as a core element of curriculums and will assist in legitimising PE as a subject where learning is taking place (Ní Chrónín and Cosgrave, 2013). However, gaps in the literature are apparent. Only limited research on how AfL use impacts students and teachers exists with an even greater dearth related to why uptake is low.

This literature review seeks to explore, analyse and synthesize existing research on the use of AfL in PE, with a focus on primary PE. This paper will begin by giving an

overview of assessment for learning terminology and summarising the available and missing literature in this field. It will then discuss the proposed benefits and barriers of AfL in primary PE. By examining the current literature in this way, this review aims to shed light on the current state of PE assessment practices, identify gaps in knowledge, and offer insights that may inform future research and interventions.

Learning from the Literature

Understanding Assessment for Learning (AfL)

Assessment forms an intrinsic part of the teaching and learning environment in classrooms. While assessment has taken many forms and evolved over time, at its core, it is a procedure designed to gather evidence on a learner's status (Ismail et al., 2022). Specifically, Assessment for Learning (AfL) refers to any assessment activities undertaken by teachers or students to gather evidence used to adapt teaching and/or learning. Adaptations are designed to meet emerging student needs and improve learning outcomes (Black and Wiliam, 1998). The benefits associated with AfL, and formative assessment have been extensively documented in seminal reviews on the late 80's and 90's. (Black and Wiliam, 1998; Crooks, 1988; Kluger and DeNisi, 1996; Leahy et al., 2005; Natriello, 1987). Since then, the validity of effect sizes on student learning have been called into question (Bennett, 2011; Lee et al., 2020). Despite this, numerous studies, including meta-analyses, have confirmed some of the earlier claimed benefits (Anders et al., 2022; Kingston and Nash, 2011; Lee et al., 2020; Sortwell et al., 2024; Wisniewski et al., 2020). However, these studies have drawn attention to the limited evidence base on AfL's efficacy. Existing analyses call for more robust research into the effectiveness of AfL accounting for contextual and educational variables involved (Sortwell et al., 2024). Nevertheless, a strong body of literature exists on components of AfL (Black and Wiliam 1998; Broadfoot et. al 2002; Schildkamp et. al., 2020;

Wiliam, 2007; Wiliam, 2024,). These components, as best described by Wiliam (2011) include but are not limited to, clarifying learning intentions, engineering effective classroom discussions, providing feedback, activating students as learning resources for one another, and activating students as owners of their learning. Various terms are used to describe these “hallmarks” of AfL. It is these components recommended in the literature that have shaped my overview of the available research on AfL in PE.

Assessment for Learning within Physical Education (PE)

As far back as 2006 (Hay), authors have called attention to limited research. Some developments have been made since then, however the incomplete research base is still consistently highlighted in the literature (Chng and Lund 2018; Leirhaug, and Annerstedt 2015). A contradictory standard in the focus of research on assessment and AfL exists. Globally assessment remains “at the fore of contemporary developments and debates” however primary PE “received relatively little attention across research and professional communities” (DinanThompson and Penney, 2015, p.1). The depth of research on embedding AfL in the classroom has not translated to similar depths of research in the PE classroom (Hay 2006). Since 2006, a growing body of research has emerged exploring teachers’ and preservice teachers’ (PSTs) attitudes towards AfL (Moura et al. 2021), as well as studies on how primary teachers use AfL to promote learning in PE (Ní Chrónín and Cosgrave 2013, Herrero-González et al., 2024).

The Prevalence and Challenges of Summative Assessment in Physical Education

PE relies heavily on summative fitness-based assessments at both primary and secondary levels, sidelining AfL (López-Pastor et al., 2013; Lorente-Catalan and Kirk, 2016; Moura et al., 2021;) critique the “the prevalence of traditional practices...where assessment is basic or non-existent” in PE despite longstanding advocacy for alternatives (2016, p.14). Plant

(2007) remarks that many practitioners get assessment ‘horribly wrong’ in physical education by only focusing on summative assessments based solely on the child’s ability to perfect skills at the end of a unit. Similarly, López-Pastor et al’s (2013) review of international literature, note that despite advances in the practical implementation of the assessment for learning model, conventional assessment models grounded in physical fitness testing continue to prevail. The situation persists at secondary level, where students are often assessed summatively and in some cases at the expense of assessment for learning (Lyngstad et. al, 2022). This is substantiated by a recent Spanish study that highlighted advancements in AfL enactment in PE yet recognised lower levels of enactment were more prevalent at primary level among younger teachers (González-Rivera et al., 2023). However, an even more recent review of a formative and shared assessment model paints a promising picture in both Spain and Chile. Herrero-González et al. (2024) highlight how the model has gained traction in all stages of education, gradually consolidating its position as a core element in PE teaching over the last 25 years.

Spain and Chile are exceptions; in contrast, the dominance in summative assessment remains widespread internationally. Why this is the case is unclear. A study of PSTs and teachers highlighted they had a narrow understanding of assessment and showed confusion between summative and formative assessment terminology (DinanThompson and Penney, 2015; Macken et al., 2020). Several recent studies on PSTs’ perceptions and use of AfL raise concerns about the lack of exposure to formative assessments experiences in PSTs’ own primary and secondary school education (Atienza et al., 2023; Lorente-Catalán and Kirk, 2016; Macken et al., 2020; Starck et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2023). Starck et al. (2023) highlight that not only do PSTs’ lack exposure to AfL, but their PE assessment experiences were “restricted to traditional forms of assessment, such as fitness testing and teacher observation.” (p. 312). Atienza et al. (2023) connected this lack of exposure to formative assessment in PSTs’ schooling to a lack of understanding of AfL concepts in their physical education teacher

education (PETE). López-Pastor et al. (2013) emphasise that many PSTs rely excessively on summative approaches to assessment, often neglecting to consider or incorporate ongoing formative assessment methods or to use that assessment evidence for formative purposes like changing teaching practice. Atienza et al. (2023) emphasise that changing the way teacher educators and PSTs teach and learn about assessment represents a “paradigmatic change” (p. 2).

Attaining parity between AoL and AfL represents a formidable challenge requiring a “considerable effort to effect change in classroom assessment practice” (MacPhail and Halbert, 2010, p. 36). As early as 2010, this need for rebalancing was recognised. Black and Wiliam (2018), key authors in the field, emphasise that viewing assessment in an integrated way is vital. A rebalancing rather than removal of one form over another addresses this. The AIESEP position statement on Assessment in PE advocates for this balance acknowledging that teachers should deploy assessment of learning “in order to periodically determine the students’ learning progress” in addition to including AfL methods (2020, p.8). Concerningly, “prevalent and dominant practices of teaching and learning” in PE actively work against “AfL and related approaches to assessment.” (Lorente-Catalán and Kirk, 2016, p. 14).

Benefits of AfL in PE

Research specifically within primary PE is limited. While some smaller scale qualitative studies in Irish and international contexts provide insights into AfL’s efficacy in PE, empirical evidence remains sparse (López-Pastor et al., 2013), necessitating a cautious interpretation of their findings.

A US based scoping review on assessment practices in PE at primary and secondary level identified three common student benefits; integration of formative assessment throughout the learning process and transparency in the assessment process benefitted skill success, with

peer assessment increasing students' enjoyment and motivation (Killian and Mays Woods 2021). However, the review was limited to 17 studies and included studies on all assessment styles not just AfL, highlighting a deficiency in evidence on teacher assessment practices and underscoring the need for “systematic research to...build a stronger foundation for evidence-based recommendations for practice” (p.1). Despite the limitations of this review, similar findings on increased student enjoyment echoed across the smaller scale qualitative studies by MacPhail and Halbert (2010), Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave (2013), and Macken and O'Leary (2008). A recent systematic literature review of 51 studies notes “the predominance of positive results in the application of formative and shared assessment, both in PE and PETE”, adding weight to the claim of the benefits of AfL in PE. (Herrero-González, 2024, p.505).

Chng and Lund (2018) in their review of literature, identify two benefits of implementation of AfL in PE: better instruction and better student learning. Analysing a small number of studies, they found use of formative assessment enhanced the quality of teaching in part due to improved planning and thus improved instruction and learning experiences for students. The Irish based Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave (2013) study highlighted students attributed a higher value to PE after engagement with AfL, recognising it as a subject where learning is taking place. Children's perception of their inclusion in the learning process focused them on learning opportunities. For teachers, the benefits centred on increasing their knowledge of assessment strategies and improving their content knowledge and understanding of skills progression. Research on assessment more generally and in other curricular areas suggests that possessing strong content knowledge is a crucial factor for effectively implementing AfL. (Herman et al., 2015; James et al., 2005; Rink et al., 2007). Schildkamp et al. (2020) goes as far as naming content knowledge a “crucial prerequisite” for effective use of formative assessment. This raises an intriguing question regarding the causal relationship:

whether AfL enhances content knowledge or if having robust content knowledge contributes to the improved delivery of AfL one requiring further interrogation in the research.

While specific to the Irish post-primary context, MacPhail and Halbert's (2010) study identifies similar benefits to Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave (2013). The importance of content knowledge was also raised; with teachers reporting increased interrogation of their planned content. Teachers similarly observed increased sentiments of student ownership over learning but went a step further and related this to the use of success criteria. Furthermore, success criteria contributed to student enjoyment of the learning process with one pupil remarking "in each lesson we had a goal to achieve unlike before when we didn't plan to achieve anything" (MacPhail and Halbert, 2010, p. 9). Perhaps most importantly, student's increasingly perceived PE as valuable after student engagement with AfL; a similar change in perception that occurred in Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave's study (2013). The shift in student perception of PE, most notably "that PE is concerned with learning, brought about by a change in teacher practice, is an important finding" of MacPhail and Halbert's work (2010, p. 36).

Barriers for AfL in PE

Several challenges that hinder successful implementation of AfL shape the landscape of educational progress in this field. DinanThompson and Penney (2015) pinpoint perhaps the most significant challenge: Assessment is viewed as low stakes in PE and flexibility is being exploited as unfettered autonomy leading to avoidance of assessment. Most concerningly, they suggest this flexibility enables the continuation of current assessment practices which are limited and dominated by summative assessment. MacPhail and Murphy (2017) echo this concern questioning if too much freedom and autonomy is afforded in the enactment of assessment in Ireland. A decade earlier, Morgan and Hansen (2007) also identified teacher avoidance of assessment in PE but attributed this to teachers' lack of knowledge and skills for

incorporating assessment in PE. On a similar point of avoidance, Graham (2008) highlights that many teachers bypass planning in PE often viewing it as unnecessary, a concern given how crucial it is to quality enactment of AfL generally (Schildkamp, 2020). Increased demands on planning were also shared as a concern of teachers embedding AfL in their PE lessons (MacPhail and Halbert, 2010) . Recent research warns that teachers need to “adjust their workload” so AfL remains feasible to implement over time (Herrero-González et. al., 2024, p.501).

When teachers do move beyond the mere avoidance of AfL, they continue to face constraints and obstacles that hinder successful enactment of AfL. A crucial issue for teachers was that of extreme time pressures (Olrich, 2002). Not only are teachers constrained by short windows of PE allocated time to conduct assessment; they also face conflicting demands to increase physical activity time in their lessons. A key concern of teachers in MacPhail and Halbert’s (2010) study was reduced physical activity levels when introducing AfL into their lessons. Due to limited research and the lack of evidence-based approaches to AfL, these legitimate concerns and competing pressures remain unresolved.

Concern for reducing students’ enjoyment in PE through AfL enactment was a key issue for teachers (Morgan and Hansen, 2007; Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave, 2013). However, this concern was largely expressed prior to AfL enactment. Teachers expressed openness to adopting formal AfL techniques but cautioned against making it overly formal (Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave, 2013). Fear of reducing fun is directly contradicted by studies showing participation in peer assessment and sharing of success criteria, key AfL strategies, increase student engagement and enjoyment (Killian and Mays Woods 2021; MacPhail and Halbert, 2010). Park (2017) raises two issues regarding implementation reducing AfL’s efficacy: recycling of previous assessment strategies and lack of appropriate feedback to students. Recycling of assessment techniques in consecutive lessons reduced student enjoyment. The

practice gives credence to the apprehension of “ruining the fun” teachers voiced concerns about (Morgan and Hansen, 2007; Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave, 2013). However, the practice can easily be avoided once the evidence is shared with teachers. Lack of appropriate feedback is perhaps more concerning, as timely specific and encouraging feedback is central to the AfL process (Wiliam, 2011; Wiliam, 2024). Inability to utilise this central AfL technique is potentially a consequence of teachers’ poor assessment literacy identified in the literature (DinanThompson and Penney, 2015). Park (2017) emphasises the need to “develop assessment literacy of teachers” to address these issues (p. 212).

While content knowledge enhances the delivery of AfL, as discussed earlier, its absence hinders the delivery of AfL. Insufficient content knowledge remains a major barrier to primary teachers assessing in PE, a concern supported by other authors (Herman et al., 2015; Rink, 2007; James et al.’s, 2005;). Moura et al.’s (2021) review of literature recognises AfL is rarely integrated into PE due to teachers’ inadequate knowledge for implementation. Beyond insufficient content knowledge, insufficient assessment literacy plays a role. Hay and Penney (2012) define assessment literacy as four components: assessment comprehension, application and interpretation and lastly, critical engagement with assessment. Two recent studies (Macken et al., 2020; Moura et al., 2023) suggest assessment literacy in PE was low. Although based on experiences of PSTs, interestingly their difficulties centred on transforming assessment practices explored in teacher education to specific school contexts. DinanThompson and Penney (2015) similarly conclude primary PE teachers have low assessment literacy levels and therefore must develop their knowledge and skills to use assessment evidence to improve students’ learning. Haycock and Smith (2010) found teachers are ill-equipped to assess students with special educational needs accurately and appropriately, a concern for inclusion and a further sign of limited assessment literacy.

Moura et al. (2021) infer that a lack of skill in enacting assessment has hindered AfL implementation in PE. Similarly, Leirhaug et. al's (2016) identified limited implementation of AfL in Norwegian PE classrooms. One reason posited was teachers failing to grasp deeper understandings of AfL. Raising assessment literacy is advised by the authors to address these deficits, although the exact form this should take remains unclear.

In summary, AfL implementation in PE raises a myriad of challenges that significantly impact its effectiveness. Teachers' view of assessment in PE as low stakes, coupled with concerns about flexibility leading to avoidance of planning for and executing assessment pose problems. Extreme time pressures and conflicting demands on PE lesson time, further compound the challenges. Additionally, apprehensions about the potential reduction of enjoyment in PE through the enactment of AfL remain, although these concerns are directly contradicted by some studies. The barriers extend to insufficient content knowledge and assessment literacy among primary PE teachers and PSTs, noted by various researchers. DeLuca et al. (2018) advocate for implementing all aspects of AfL collectively to increase efficacy. Addressing the complexity of these challenges requires targeted efforts to rectify each identified barrier, a daunting prospect given the breadth and range of issues. Optimistically, MacPhail and Murphy (2017) argue that "this complexity, while applicable to many aspects of teaching physical education, need not constitute 'the roadblock' that it has represented traditionally" making the case for further study on appropriate professional development to address this challenge (p. 246).

Support for AfL in PE

Support is required to rebalance the assessment landscape in PE. As noted earlier, assessment practices in PE have remained largely unchanged over the past 30 years despite growing research underpinning the importance of AfL in classrooms (Lorente-Catalán and Kirk

2016). At this juncture intervention is required. AIESEP (2020) considers it essential that research is aimed at building the currently sparse evidence base identifying supports for PE teachers' assessment practices. These interventions could help build the evidence base for the most effective supports for integrating AfL into teachers' practice and improving assessment literacy.

Practical strategies advised in the literature supporting AfL enactment are wide ranging and attempt to address key difficulties. For instance, to combat time pressures, an early study on formative assessment by Olrich (2002) suggests formative assessments by design save time as they are delivered throughout the learning period of a lesson. This contrasts with summative assessments, which are often concentrated at the end. Utilising peer assessment and integrating technology into assessment practices are offered as realistic solutions to maximising teacher time while enacting AfL. A more recent meta-analysis repeats the same advice, advocating further for technology to assist with time consuming peer and self-assessments (Herrero-González et al; 2024). A recent study by González-Rivera et al. (2023) highlighted the strong link between effective planning and effective assessment suggesting support with planning may encourage quality teaching and assessment. Teachers recognise this importance of effective planning; however, planning requires dedication of teachers' time (Herrero-González, 2024; Morgan et. al, 2019;). Any work to support planning, however, may be underpinned by the earlier research finding of MacPhail and Halbert (2010) who recommended reducing the volume of paper-based tasks.

Starck et al. (2023) make the point that PSTs lack extensive experiences with assessment during their own schooling and as such physical education teacher education (PETE) faculty members should first help them understand the purpose of assessment before building on this to improve more complex aspects of assessment literacy. Improving teachers' ability to determine how best to use assessment evidence to improve students' learning is

needed to support the implementation of AfL (DinanThompson, 2013). The research has not clearly established what form support should take to promote development in these areas. Several studies found modelling, scaffolding, and mentoring from teacher educators increased assessment literacy levels among PSTs (Macken et al., 2020; Moura et al., 2023). Teachers face many challenges in the enactment of AfL and in the case of PSTs, they often react to these challenges with reluctance and avoidance of AfL (Macken et al., 2020). PETE programmes should include “greater opportunities to reflect on the complexities, rather than solely...the benefits of employing AfL” to address PSTs reluctance effectively (2020, p. 552). Moura et. al (2023) suggest PE educators can promote assessment literacy beyond the PETE context, advising teacher educators to connect with teachers in schools. Ongoing support is crucial for these educators to reshape their assessment practices (Moura et al., 2021). The AIESEP Position Statement on Physical Education Assessment (2020, p,9) makes explicit reference to “a sufficient level of support and autonomy” teachers require to translate assessment theory into practice that meets students at their level in an inclusive and equitable way.

The scarcity of teachers using AfL in PE may be explained, in part, by the deficit in support and networks. (Moura et al., 2021). Essentially, teachers lack networks for enabling them to develop their use of AfL in PE contexts (Herrero-González, 2024; Lorente-Catalán and Kirk, 2016; MacPhail and Murphy, 2017). Lorente-Catalán and Kirk (2016) highlight that PE teachers supporting each other in their understanding and enactment of AfL and sharing related difficulties and strategies is crucial to their success in implementing AfL in their teaching. Ní Chróinín and Cosgrave (2013) stress “that content knowledge should be a fundamental consideration for any initiative intending to use assessment as a lever to enhance teaching and learning” (p. 226). Designing networks supporting teachers’ enactment of AfL may facilitate discussions specifically on AfL and open opportunities to discuss various interrelated areas that contribute to effective implementation of AfL, namely content knowledge.

Review Limitations

Although literature on AfL enactment in PE is sparse internationally, a particularly pronounced paucity of studies conducted in Ireland exists. This review draws heavily from American, Spanish and South American literature, posing significant contextual challenges for any generalisations that can be made to Irish educational settings. During a period of curriculum reform in Ireland, empirical and qualitative evidence on how Irish teachers use AfL is missing from the arena, and with it much needed nuance. MacPhail and Murphy (2017) assert that Irish studies on Irish PE need to investigate both teachers' and students' exposure and engagement with AfL. Teacher education programmes also have a responsibility to lead change in AfL practices. Recent research on AfL in PE on Irish PETE programmes (Macken, 2020) advocates for further studies exploring the most effective ways initial teacher education can instil assessment literacy. The more pronounced paucity of literature investigating AfL in PE in Ireland, emphasises the tentative nature of any conclusions that can be drawn about this aspect of PE. More research is needed on how Irish teachers, students and PSTs engage with AfL in the context of ongoing curricular reforms.

Conclusion

In conclusion, implementing AfL in PE presents significant challenges rooted in longstanding assessment practices and limited support structures. Despite growing research advocating for AfL, the field remains largely unchanged in PE, particularly within the Irish context. Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions to enhance PE teachers' assessment literacy, support effective planning and implementation of AfL strategies, and foster collaborative networks among educators. A critical need exists for ongoing professional development and research initiatives tailored to Irish educational settings to effectively integrate AfL, ensuring it enhances teaching quality and student achievement in PE.

Reference List

- AIESEP (2020) ‘AIESEP Position Statement on Physical Education Assessment’. Available at: <https://aiesep.org/scientific-meetings/position-statements/> (Accessed: 2 May 2024).
- Anders, J., Foliano, F., Bursnall, M., Dorsett, R., Hudson, N., Runge, J., Speckesser, S., 2022. The Effect of Embedding Formative Assessment on Pupil Attainment. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness* 15, 748–779. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19345747.2021.2018746>
- Atienza, R., Valencia-Peris, A. & López-Pastor, V.M. (2023) ‘Formative assessment and pre-service teacher education: previous, current and prospective experiences’, *Cultura, Ciencia y Deporte*, 18(55). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12800/ccd.v18i55.1914>.
- Bennett, R.E., 2011. Formative assessment: a critical review. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* 18, 5–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2010.513678>
- Black, P.J. & Wiliam, D. (1998) *Inside the Black Box: Raising Standards Through Classroom Assessment*. London: GL Assessment.
- Broadfoot, P., Daugherty, R., Gardner, J., Harlen, W., James, M., Stobart, G., 2002. *Assessment for Learning: 10 Principles. Research-based principles to guide classroom practice*. Assessment for Learning.
- Chng, L.S. & Lund, J. (2018) ‘Assessment for Learning in Physical Education: The What, Why and How’, *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation and Dance*, 89(8), pp. 29–34. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2018.1503119>.
- Crooks, T.J. (1988) ‘The Impact of Classroom Evaluation Practices on Students’, *Review of Educational Research*, 58(4), pp. 438–481. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1170281>.

- DeLuca, C., Chapman-Chin, A.E.A., LaPointe-McEwan, D., Klinger, D.A., 2018. Student perspectives on assessment for learning. *The Curriculum Journal* 29, 77–94.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585176.2017.1401550>
- Dinan-Thompson, M. & Penney, D. (2015) ‘Assessment literacy in primary physical education’, *European Physical Education Review*, 21(4), pp. 485–503. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X15584087>.
- Dinan-Thompson, M. (2013) ‘Claiming “educative outcomes” in HPE: the potential for “pedagogic action”’, *Asia-Pacific Journal of Health, Sport and Physical Education*, 4(2), pp. 127–142. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/18377122.2013.801106>.
- González-Rivera, M.-D. et al. (2023) ‘Planning and assessment practices among Spanish physical education teachers according to experience and teaching level’, *European Physical Education Review*, 29(3), pp. 438–454. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X231158916>.
- Graham, G. (2008) *Teaching Children Physical Education: Becoming a Master Teacher*. 3rd edn. Human Kinetics.
- Hay, P. and Penney, D. (2012) *Assessment in Physical Education*. 0 edn. Routledge. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203133163>.
- Hay, P.J. (2006) ‘Assessment for Learning in Physical Education’, in Kirk, D., Macdonald, D. & O’Sullivan, M. (eds) *Handbook of Physical Education*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd, pp. 312–325. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848608009.n18>.
- Haycock, D. & Smith, A. (2010) ‘Inadequate and Inappropriate?: The Assessment of Young Disabled People and Pupils with Special Educational Needs in National Curriculum

Physical Education’, *European Physical Education Review*, 16(3), pp. 283–300.

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X10382975>.

Herman, J. *et al.* (2015) ‘Investigating the dynamics of formative assessment: relationships between teacher knowledge, assessment practice and learning’, *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 22(3), pp. 344–367. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2015.1006521>.

Herrero-González, D. *et al.* (2024) ‘Formative and shared assessment: Literature review on the main contributions in physical education and physical education teacher education’, *European Physical Education Review*, 30(3), pp. 493–510. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X231220995>.

Ismail, S. M., Rahul, D. R., Patra, I., & Rezvani, E. (2022). Formative vs. summative assessment: Impacts on academic motivation, attitude toward learning, test anxiety, and self-regulation skill. *Language Testing in Asia*, 12(1), 40.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-022-00191-4>

James, A.R., Griffin, L.L. & France, T. (2005) ‘Perceptions of assessment in elementary physical education: A case study’, *Physical Educator*, 62(2), pp. 85–95.

Killian, C.M. & Mays Woods, A. (2021) ‘Assessment Practices in K–12 Physical Education in the United States: A Scoping Review of Research, 2000–2020’, *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 92(2), pp. 248–258. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2021.1894315>.

Kingston, N. & Nash, B. (2011) ‘Formative Assessment: A Meta-Analysis and a Call for Research’, *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 30(4), pp. 28–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3992.2011.00220.x>.

- Kluger, A.N. & DeNisi, A. (1996) 'The Effects of Feedback Interventions on Performance: A Historical Review, A Meta-Analysis, and a Preliminary Feedback Intervention Theory', *Psychological Bulletin*, 119(2), pp. 254–284. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.119.2.254>.
- Leahy, S., Lyon, C., Thompson, M. & Wiliam, D. (2005) 'Classroom assessment: Minute by minute, day by day', *Educational Leadership*, 63(3), pp. 19–24.
- Lee, H. *et al.* (2020) 'The Effectiveness and Features of Formative Assessment in US K-12 Education: A Systematic Review', *Applied Measurement in Education*, 33(2), pp. 124–140. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08957347.2020.1732383>.
- Leirhaug, P.E. & Annerstedt, C. (2015) 'Assessing with new eyes? Assessment for learning in Norwegian physical education', *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 21(6), pp. 616–631. doi: 10.1080/17408989.2015.1095871.
- López-Pastor, V.M. *et al.* (2013) 'Alternative Assessment in Physical Education: A Review of International Literature', *Sport, Education and Society*, 18(1), pp. 57–76. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2012.713860>.
- Lorente-Catalán, E. & Kirk, D. (2016) 'Student Teachers' Understanding and Application of Assessment for Learning During a Physical Education Teacher Education Course', *European Physical Education Review*, 22(1), pp. 65–81. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X15590352>.
- Lyngstad, I. *et al.* (2022) 'Norwegian upper secondary students' experiences of their teachers' assessment of and for learning in physical education: examining how assessment is interpreted by students of different physical abilities', *Sport, Education and Society*, 27(3), pp. 320–331. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2020.1842728>.

- Macken, S. and O'Leary, M. (2008) 'Assessment for learning in primary physical education: the experiences of student teachers', *European Physical Education Review*, 14(3), pp. 299–315. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X08092596>.
- Macken, S., MacPhail, A. & Calderon, A. (2020) 'Exploring Primary Pre-Service Teachers' Use of "Assessment for Learning" While Teaching Primary Physical Education During School Placement', *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 25(5), pp. 539–554. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2020.1752647>.
- MacPhail, A. & Halbert, J. (2010) "'We Had to Do Intelligent Thinking During Recent PE": Students' and Teachers' Experiences of Assessment for Learning in Post-Primary Physical Education', *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 17(1), pp. 23–39. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09695940903565412>.
- MacPhail, A. & Murphy, F. (2017) 'Too much freedom and autonomy in the enactment of assessment? Assessment in physical education in Ireland', *Irish Educational Studies*, 36(2), pp. 237–252. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2017.1327365>.
- Morgan, K., Bryant, A.S., Edwards, L.C., Mitchell-Williams, E., 2019. Transferring primary generalists' positive classroom pedagogy to the physical education setting: a collaborative PE-CPD process. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy* 24, 43–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2018.1533543>
- Morgan, P. & Hansen, V. (2007) 'Recommendations to Improve Primary School Physical Education: Classroom Teachers' Perspective', *The Journal of Educational Research*, 101(2), pp. 99–108. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3200/JOER.101.2.99-112>.

- Moura, A. et al. (2021) 'Aligning the Principles of Assessment for Learning to Learning in Physical Education: A Review of Literature', *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 26(4), pp. 388–401. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2020.1834528>.
- Moura, A. et al. (2023) 'Providing Physical Education Preservice Teachers with Opportunities to Interrogate Their Conceptions and Practices of Assessment', *European Physical Education Review*, 29(1), pp. 162–179. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X221129057>.
- Natriello, G. (1987) 'The Impact of Evaluation Processes on Students', *Educational Psychologist*, 22(2), pp. 155–175. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep2202_4.
- Ní Chróinín, D. & Cosgrave, C. (2013) 'Implementing Formative Assessment in Primary Physical Education: Teacher Perspectives and Experiences', *Physical Education & Sport Pedagogy*, 18(2), pp. 219–233. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2012.666787>.
- Olrich, T.W. (2002) 'Assessing Fundamental Motor Skills in the Elementary School Setting: Issues and Solutions', *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 73(7), pp. 26–28. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2002.10607843>.
- Park, Y. (2017) 'Examining South Korea's Elementary Physical Education Performance Assessment Using Assessment for Learning', *Asia-Pacific Journal of Health, Sport and Physical Education*, 8(3), pp. 257–272. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/18377122.2017.1364676>.
- Plant, I. (2007) The complex nature of assessment. *Physical Education Matters*, 2(2), pp. 26–27. In J. E. Rink (Ed.), *Teaching physical education for learning* (pp. 26–27). St. Louis, MO: Mosby Year-Book.

- Rink, J. et al. (2007) 'Teacher Perceptions of a Physical Education Statewide Assessment Program', *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 78(3), pp. 204–215. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2007.10599418>.
- Schildkamp, K. et al. (2020) 'Formative assessment: A systematic review of critical teacher prerequisites for classroom practice', *International Journal of Educational Research*, 103, p. 101602. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101602>.
- Sortwell, A., Trimble, K., Ferraz, R., Geelan, D.R., Hine, G., Ramirez-Campillo, R., Carter-Thuiller, B., Gkintoni, E., Xuan, Q., 2024. A Systematic Review of Meta-Analyses on the Impact of Formative Assessment on K-12 Students' Learning: Toward Sustainable Quality Education. *Sustainability* 16, 7826. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16177826>
- Starck, J.R., O'Neil, K.M. & Richards, K.A. (2023) 'Preservice Teachers' Perceptions of and Intentions to Utilize Assessment', *Curriculum Studies in Health and Physical Education*, pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/25742981.2023.2240300>.
- Wei, G., Lee, H.-Y. & Chung, C.-Y. (2023) 'Developing Pre-Service Teachers' Practical Knowledge Through Formative Interventions', *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 49(3), pp. 384–400. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2022.2111515>.
- Wiliam, D. (2007) 'Keeping learning on track: Formative assessment and the regulation of learning', Presentation at the Assessment for Learning Conference. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/252646685_Keeping_learning_on_track_Formative_assessment_and_the_regulation_of_learning (Accessed: 18 July 2024).
- Wiliam, D. (2024) *Embedding Formative Assessment: Practical Techniques for K-12 Classrooms (Practical Formative Assessment Techniques for K-12 Classrooms)*. 1st ed. Bloomington, Indiana: Solution Tree.

Wiliam, D., 2011. Embedded formative assessment. Solution Tree Press, Bloomington, IN.

Wisniewski, B., Zierer, K., Hattie, J., 2020. The Power of Feedback Revisited: A Meta-Analysis of Educational Feedback Research. *Front. Psychol.* 10, 3087.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03087>